

Rural property management platform

Introduction

The change in population and land use in the Spanish rural forest environment in recent decades has led to the abandonment of large areas with the potential to be put to good use, which requires the design of new management models and proposals for solutions to facilitate access to their productive revaluation. Those areas whose management is limited due to their size and/or the difficulty of knowing their ownership, constitute a large number of hectares that can add value to rural areas, for which administrations, owners and other agents involved must work together in the innovative implementation of solutions. The Rustic Property Management Platform is a web tool designed to facilitate the management of rustic plots, both agricultural and forestry, and help their owners to manage their plots, as well as to contact other owners with whom they want to interact either by associating or through the purchase, sale, exchange or lease of plots. Through this platform you will be able to administer the management of your rustic plots, both agricultural and forestry, as well as to get in touch with other owners with whom you want to interact either by joining or by buying, selling, exchanging or leasing plots.

The tool allows: (1) Carry out an inventory, stock and profitability analysis of an owner's rustic holdings through tabular and geographical consultation tools in a map viewer. (2) Promote the exchange or swapping of properties that favors their grouped management. Register plots of land in a rural holdings registration service. (3) Access a service for the generation of agreements for the transfer, custody, rental or lease of rural real estate between owners or managers. (4) Access information on fire risk and territorial zoning (regional, municipal or other) that may affect forestry treatments, exploitation and/or post-fire restoration, as well as funding through subsidies or aid in relation to this zoning. (5) Obtain information about forest fire damage coverage. (6) Obtain information on the times of danger with a view to regulating uses and requesting permits.

Specifically, the user would be able to: (1) Access cadastral rustic plots of land throughout Spain to: Register the plots of your property, create holdings by grouping your plots to manage them more easily and create groupings of owners to manage your plots together. (2) Access the Plot Announcement Service: Where you can create advertisements to buy, sell, lease or exchange plots of land, you can also create announcements to form groups of owners, access the ads of other registered owners and get in touch with them to make transactions. (3) Access the geographic viewer with information about your plot: Current vegetation, suitability of your plot for other vegetation, potential assessment of the profitability of your plot, fire risk, regulations and protected areas.

Lessons learned

The atomisation of land ownership and the need for a tool, to facilitate the management of these plots, makes it necessary to develop a digital tool to help facilitate this management. The smallholding management platform proposes a range of innovative solutions, such as having prior information on the characteristics of the plots in terms of their dendrometric possibilities and productive potential. The platform incorporates the possibility of grouping plots from different owners and being able to be managed as a group of producers or owners. However, in order to be used, it is necessary to add forestry references and to be able to document forestry operations under forest planning instruments. Therefore, there is a need to develop the appropriate software for the tool, enabling the management of these plots according to the technical management plans or associated forestry references. It is also necessary to extend the tool, making it possible to have all the spatial information of the management plans available. In the agricultural field, the tool needs to develop a digital version of the field notebook as an additional utility. Finally, a mobile application with offline functionality is necessary to complete its implementation.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://gestion.minifundio.es/>

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